

An Intergenerational Comparison of Coping Styles and Perception of Stress

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This research paper delves into the comparative analysis of coping styles and perception of stress among two distinct generations in India, Generation Z (18-27 years) and Generation X (44-59 years). Drawing from the theoretical frameworks of Lazarus and Folkman (1984) and Endler and Parker (1992) this study investigates the coping mechanisms employed by each generation in response to stressors, along with their perception of stress. The aim of this study is to assess and compare intergenerational coping styles and perception of stress in an Indian sample. The study involved 200 participants of Indian nationality from two different age groups- Gen X (49-59 years) and Gen Z (18-28 years), who were recruited through snowball sampling. They were administered the Brief-COPE inventory and the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10) to assess coping styles and perception of stress respectively. The results were analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), version 29.0. The findings of the t-test showed that while there was no significant difference found in the perception of stress between the two age groups, there were significant disparities in coping strategies, particularly in acceptance, behavioural disengagement, and substance abuse. While Generation X exhibits a higher tendency towards acceptance, Generation Z displays elevated rates of behavioural disengagement and substance misuse, indicating a concerning reliance on maladaptive coping mechanisms among the younger cohort. While no significant difference was found in the perception of stress between the two age groups, notable distinctions emerged in coping mechanisms.

Keywords: Intergenerational comparison, coping style, perception of stress, generation X, generation Y

According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2023), stress can be defined as “a state of worry or mental tension caused by a difficult situation.” The factors causing stress are known as stressors and can be of various types, including environmental (extreme temperatures, noise, illumination), physical (illness, disease, impairment), social (conflicting relationships) as well as psychological (faulty patterns of thought, unrealistic beliefs) (National Council of Educational research & Training, 2017). Besides the stressor itself, an individual's perception of the stressful event, as well as the coping strategies used in the face of it, also contribute to the experience of stress (National Council of Educational research & Training, 2017). Coping is a dynamic situation-specific reaction to stress and the way an individual copes with stress largely depends on past experiences, conditioned responses to stressful situations, and personal values and beliefs (National Council of Educational research & Training, 2017). Lazarus and Folkman (1984) identified two basic coping styles-

Problem-oriented Coping: This involves obtaining information

about the stressful situation, looking for possible courses of action, and actively engaging to deal with the stressful situation. For example, following a set schedule of tasks every day to meet a deadline.

Emotion-oriented Coping: This involves dealing with one's emotional response to the stressful situation. This may occur in the form of venting feelings of anger or frustration, emotional withdrawal or self-blame, or may occur in the form of active efforts to manage extreme emotions and maintain hope before dealing with the stressful event.

Endler and Parker (1992) have identified another major coping style-Avoidance-oriented coping. This involves engaging in substitute tasks or distracting activities or seeing out other people to deny or minimize the seriousness of the situation. For example, playing video games to avoid sitting down to study for a test. A fourth coping style includes, meaning-focused coping style, which involves the use of cognitive strategies to derive and manage the meaning of the situation (Algorani & Gupta, 2023).

Rattan et al. (2023) have found that there is a strong negative correlation between perceived stress and subjective well-being, which implies that in the earlier studies by Folkman et al. the younger population also had a higher level of perceived stress. Gursoy and Toksoy (2023) found that an individual's perception to stress and use of coping styles can affect their resilience in stressful situations. The study also found that indulging in social support seeking behaviour during stressful times can help enhance well-being, while acceptance behaviour can build resilience. Certain coping mechanisms may be positively correlated to both avoidant coping styles and problem-focused coping styles, for example, humour. Simione and Gnagnarella (2023) have found that humour can help reduce perceived stress when used in medium to high

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amounts in a stressful situation. The study also found that, there is a weak negative correlation between humour and perceived stress, which could be because humour is sometimes used to avoid dealing with stress. In a study involving teachers, Daniilidou (2023) found that the primary stressors in the participants involved job-related issues (decreased salary, lack of job security & increased workload) and issues with students (increased number of children with learning difficulties & behavioural changes). The study found that the teachers engaged in a number of strategies to deal with such stressors and to increase their resilience, including individual efforts (which involved problem-oriented coping strategies such as time management, trial-&-error method, decision making etc.), efforts to seek outside help (which involved seeking informational & psychological assistance from colleagues or other contacts outside the work environment) and compromising, accepting or resigning from the job. The sample in the study, which mostly involved middle adulthood, thus engaged primarily in active problem-oriented coping, followed by social/instrumental support strategies and lastly acceptance or passive coping styles. Daniilidou (2023) also found that only people above 37 years of age engaged in strategies to distance themselves emotionally and physically from the issue/problem. While some studies suggest that younger individuals display less resilience than older individuals (Harari et al., 2022) such a conclusion is domain or context-dependent and cannot be generalized across all scenarios. Harari et al. (2022) for example, conducted a comparative study of Generation X and Generation Z participants and found that Generation Z participants demonstrated lower resilience in the face of the COVID-19 and more vulnerability to mental health issues from the stress experienced during the pandemic compared to their counterparts from Generation X, with Generation Z individuals also displaying more openness to change and adherence to COVID-19 restrictions. Both strategies observed in the study are problem-oriented techniques- while Generation X individuals used them less, they displayed more resilience and reported lesser mental health issues compared to their Generation Z counterparts. This could be a result of underreporting of data on behalf of the Generation X participants, especially when it comes to acknowledging mental health issues, something that the younger populations have normalized much more. Thus, over the years, several factors, such as changes in work patterns, general lifestyle and sociocultural scenarios across countries, have collectively evolved to contribute to more complex stressors. Due to a growing recognition of and concern for mental health, there has been an increase in reports of stress levels among the Indian population. According to the India Wellness Index by ICICI Lombard General Insurance (2023) every third person in India is grappling with stress. According to the same report, 77% of Indians face at least one symptom of stress regularly, with Gen Z and millennials being far more prone to stress than the older generations. According to the GOQii India Fit Report's (2022- 2023) Stress and Mental Health Study, 26% of Indians are stressed due to their current work situation and 17% due to financial instability. 14% are stressed due to relationship troubles. From the above mentioned statistics, it can be observed that younger Indians, particularly from the Gen Z group, are by far more likely to be prone to stress. Generational differences in the experiencing of stress, thus, do exist. What remains to be considered here, however, is whether besides the stressors themselves, individual differences in perception of stress

and subsequent coping styles have a role to play in the increasing levels of stress faced by the Indian population, and whether these differences (if any) are influenced in any manner by generation-specific factors such as age, socioeconomic factors, work and social life experiences and relationships. The aim of this study was to assess and compare coping styles and perception of stress among individuals belonging to two different generations: Gen X and Gen Z. The study will help understand if within an Indian sample, certain coping styles in stressful situations are dominant in individuals in relation to the generation they belong to. It will also help understand if perception to stress is different in both generations.

Objectives of the Study

- To assess the coping styles and perception of stress in individuals belonging to Gen Z (18-27 years) of Indian nationality.
- To assess the coping styles and perception of stress among individuals belonging to Gen X (44-59 years) of Indian nationality.
- To compare coping styles and perception of stress among both groups of individuals.

Hypotheses of the Study

- There will be a significant difference in coping styles between Generation X and Generation Z.
- There will be a significant difference in perception of stress between Generation X and Generation Z.

Method

Participants

The aim of the study was to assess and compare coping styles and perception of stress observed in Indians belonging to two different generations, irrespective of gender: Gen X (49-59 years) and Gen Z (18-28 years). The participants for the sample were collected through snowball sampling method, which is a type of non-probability sampling technique using networks of friends and knowns to collect data for a study. The questionnaires were distributed to a network of friends, family members and other known associates who were asked to further spread it within their own networks.

Inclusion Criteria

- Individuals aged in the range of 44-59 years.
- Individuals aged in the range of 18-27 years.
- Individuals who are Indian by nationality.

Exclusion Criteria

- Individuals who have not completed higher secondary level of education.
- Individuals who have been diagnosed with a mental health issue.

Measures

The Brief-COPE Inventory: The Brief Coping Orientation to Problems Experienced (COPE) Inventory was adapted by Carver (1997) and is an abbreviated version of the full COPE Inventory created by Carver et al. (1989). The Brief COPE is comprised of 14 scales, each of which assesses the degree to which a respondent utilizes a specific coping strategy. Respondents rate items on a 4-

point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (*I have not been doing this at all*) to 4 (*I have been doing this a lot*). Total scores on each scale range from 2 to 8. Higher scores indicate increased utilization of that specific coping strategy. The minimum age required to take the questionnaire is 18 years. There is no upper age limit. Total scores on each of the scales are calculated by summing the appropriate items for each scale. There is no overall total score. Several studies have collapsed the coping scales into various categorizations of coping styles. However, the test developers do not have a standard rule of how to generate these categorizations and instead leave this to the user's discretion. The Brief-COPE inventory has a high level of reliability (Cronbach's alpha- 0.72 to 0.82) and appropriate construct validity (Wise et al., 2023).

Perceived Stress Scale: The Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10), developed by Cohen et al. (1983) is used for measuring the perception of stress. It is a measure of the degree to which situations in one's life are appraised as stressful. Items were designed to tap how unpredictable, uncontrollable, and overloaded respondents find their lives. The questions in the PSS ask about feelings and thoughts during the last month. In each case, respondents are asked to respond on a five-point scale from 'never' to 'very often'. Answers are then scored as follows: *Never* = 0; *Almost never* = 1; *Sometimes* = 2; *Fairly often* = 3; and *Very often* = 4. To calculate a total PSS score, responses to four items (items 4, 5, 7, & 8) first need to be reversed. The PSS score is then obtained by summing across all items. Higher scores indicate higher levels of perceived stress. There are two subscales in the PSS-10: perceived helplessness and lack of self-efficacy. The PSS-10 has been shown to have a good internal consistency in both adults and university student populations, as reviewed by Lee (2012). Test-retest reliability was found to be adequate in adults over a 2-week and 4-week period (Lee, 2012). A systematic review by Lee (2012) indicates that the PSS-10 tends to consist of two factors in adult and university student populations: Perceived Helplessness and Perceived Self-Efficacy. Similar findings were found in Chinese adolescents (Liu et al. 2020) and American adolescents (Kechter et al. 2019) indicating good construct validity.

Statistical Analysis

The data was analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), version 29.0. A t-test was carried out to compare the coping styles and perception of stress of both generations; Generation Z

refers to the 18-27 years age range and Generation X refers to the 44-59 years age range. In case of coping styles, the intergeneration comparison was done for all 14 coping styles assessed by the Brief-COPE Inventory.

Procedure

The specific research methods used in this study include the administration of one Google Form with two different questionnaires. The participants were administered two questionnaires using Google Forms, which were distributed by email or other means of online communication. The form shall contain three main parts:

- The first part consists of details regarding the objectives and subject of the study. Here, the participants shared their demographic information, including name, age, sex, educational qualification, etc.
- The second part contains the Brief-COPE inventory, wherein participants were required to read the statements and select the response which they found most accurate with relation to themselves.
- The third part contains the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10), where the participants were again required to read the statements and select an option which they found most applicable to themselves.

All details regarding inclusion criteria and conditions to qualify as a participant were conveyed to the participant at the time of distribution of Google Forms. They were also asked to share these details with others when sharing the forms. All forms which contained a response in the positive for a mental health diagnosis were rejected. This was to prevent any effect of extreme mental health issues upon stress perception. Responses by participants who did not fulfil the necessary conditions for participation were eliminated. The collection of data continued until a total of 200 responses (100 from each age group) by eligible participants were collected.

Results

A t-test was carried out to compare the coping styles and perception of stress of both generations; Generation Z refers to the 18-27 years age range and Generation X refers to the 44-59 years age range using SPSS. The following findings were obtained:

	Age	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error Mean
Acceptance	18-27	100	3.4800	.88169	.08817
	44-59	100	3.1000	1.11464	.11146
Emotional/Social Support	18-27	100	3.0400	1.00423	.10042
	44-59	100	3.1000	1.00000	.10000
Humour	18-27	100	2.8400	.99209	.09921
	44-59	100	2.6400	.93765	.09377
Positive Reframing	18-27	100	3.3200	.95219	.09522
	44-59	100	3.4000	.92113	.09211
Religion	18-27	100	2.9200	1.00182	.10018
	44-59	100	2.8600	.99514	.09951
Active Coping	18-27	100	3.5000	.87039	.08704
	44-59	100	3.5600	.83267	.08327
Instrumental Support	18-27	100	3.1800	.98862	.09886
	44-59	100	3.0800	1.00182	.10018

	44-59	100	3.0800	1.00182	.10018
Planning	18-27	100	3.2600	.97047	.09705
	44-59	100	3.4700	.96875	.09688
Behavioural Disengagement	18-27	100	2.6200	.92965	.09296
	44-59	100	2.3000	.71774	.07177
Denial	18-27	100	2.6600	.94516	.09452
	44-59	100	2.6000	.92113	.09211
Self-Distracton	18-27	100	3.2400	.97566	.09757
	44-59	100	3.0600	1.00323	.10032
Self-Blame	18-27	100	3.2200	.98041	.09804
	44-59	100	2.7000	.95874	.09587
Venting	18-27	100	2.8800	.99778	.09978
	44-59	100	2.8400	.99209	.09921
Substance Abuse	18-27	100	2.5400	.89239	.08924
	44-59	100	2.3400	.75505	.07551

Table 2

Independent Sample Test for Coping Styles in Both Age Groups

		t-scores	df	Mean difference	Standard error difference
Acceptance	Equal variances assumed	2.674*	198	.38000	.14212
	Equal variances not assumed	2.674	188.032	.38000	.14212
Emotional/Social Support	Equal variances assumed	-.423	198	-.06000	.14172
	Equal variances not assumed	-.423	197.996	-.06000	.14172
Humour	Equal variances assumed	1.465	198	.20000	.13651
	Equal variances not assumed	1.465	197.373	.20000	.13651
Positive Reframing	Equal variances assumed	-.604	198	-.08000	.13248
	Equal variances not assumed	-.604	197.783	-.08000	.13248
Religion	Equal variances assumed	.425	198	.06000	.14121
	Equal variances not assumed	.425	197.991	.06000	.14121
Active Coping	Equal variances assumed	-.498	198	-.06000	.12045
	Equal variances not assumed	-.498	197.613	-.06000	.12045
Instrumental Support	Equal variances assumed	.710	198	.10000	.14075
	Equal variances not assumed	.710	197.965	.10000	.14075
Planning	Equal variances assumed	-1.531	198	-.21000	.13712
	Equal variances not assumed	-1.531	197.999	-.21000	.13712
Behavioural Disengagement	Equal variances assumed	2.725*	198	.32000	.11745
	Equal variances not assumed	2.725	186.082	.32000	.11745
Denial	Equal variances assumed	.455	198	.06000	.13198
	Equal variances not assumed	.455	197.869	.06000	.13198
Self-Distracton	Equal variances assumed	1.286	198	.18000	.13994
	Equal variances not assumed	1.286	197.847	.18000	.13994
Self-Blame	Equal variances assumed	3.792	198	.52000	.13713
	Equal variances not assumed	3.792	197.901	.52000	.13713
Venting	Equal variances assumed	.284	198	.04000	.14071
	Equal variances not assumed	.284	197.994	.04000	.14071
Substance Abuse	Equal variances assumed	1.711*	198	.20000	.11690
	Equal variances not assumed	1.711	192.716	.20000	.11690

Note. $P < 0.001$

Table 3

Group Statistics of the PSS-10

	Age	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
PSS-10	18-27	100	2.5400	.74427	.07443
	44-59	100	2.1500	.74366	.07437

From Table 2, it is seen that there is a significant difference in Generations X and Z in terms of three coping styles- acceptance ($t=2.674$), behavioural disengagement ($t=2.725$) and substance

abuse ($t=1.711$). There is no significant difference in both age groups in terms of other coping styles.

Table 4
Independent Sample Test of the PSS-10

		t	df	Mean difference	Standard error difference
PSS-10	Equal variances assumed	3.707	198	.39000	.10521
	Equal variances not assumed	3.707	198.000	.39000	.10521

From Table 4, it can be observed that there is no significant difference in both samples in terms of perception of stress ($t=3.707$).

Discussion

The aim of this study was to compare coping styles and perception of stress among individuals belonging to two different generations- Generation Z (18-27 years) and Generation X (44-59 years). Some of the earlier studies on age differences in stress have been conducted to specifically examine differences in the experience of major life events. Studies have found that the younger population experiences more major life events compared to their older counterparts and experiences more significant effects of stress from everyday hassles, with subjective well-being and health outcomes being particularly affected (Folkman et al., 1987). Age-related changes in coping mechanisms have been interpreted in a developmental, contextual and cohort manner (Folkman et al., 1987). In the developmental interpretation, studies have found instances supporting the claim that people resort to more primitive coping mechanisms as they age, while others have found that people become more mature in their coping styles with age. On the other hand, the contextual interpretation focuses on how a change in the type of stressors with age can impact the use of certain coping mechanisms. Folkman and Lazarus (1980) conducted a study in which they found that health issues were a factor of stress faced by both younger and older populations (albeit more in case of the older individuals), however, both groups did not differ significantly in their use of emotion-focused and problem-focused coping. Additionally, a cohort interpretation of age-related changes in coping emphasizes that people belonging to different age groups differ in coping due to the experience of different historical and cultural contexts. From the results obtained in this research, it has been found that there is no significant difference in perception of stress among both age groups. However, there is a significant difference in both age groups in terms of three specific coping mechanisms- acceptance, behavioural disengagement and substance abuse. Acceptance refers to the coping mechanism by which individuals accept the reality of a situation and do not try to change the event itself. Gursoy and Toksoy (2023) found that an individual's perception of stress and use of coping styles can affect their resilience in stressful situations. The study also found that indulging in social support-seeking behaviour during stressful times can help enhance well-being, while acceptance behaviour can build resilience. The use of specific coping strategies can also impact academic endeavours and achievements of students, especially those pursuing distance courses, with informational support playing an important role in helping students deal with academic pressures while tending to their other social, religious and cultural roles

(Segbenya & Anokye, 2022). There is a positive correlation between active problem-focused coping and emotional intelligence as well as an inverse relationship between passive coping styles, as observed in young adults (Fteiha & Awwad, 2020). Thus, the higher one's emotional intelligence, the higher the possibility of an individual engaging more in active problem-oriented coping in order to deal with a stressor. According to Carver (1997), acceptance comes under the emotion-focused coping style. Out of a total 100 participants from each age group, 56 participants from Generation Z scored 6-8 (high-very high) in acceptance and 60 participants from Generation X scored within the same range in acceptance. Thus, individuals from Generation X displayed slightly more chances of resorting to acceptance than their Generation Z counterparts. Nakamura and Orth (2005) have found that while active acceptance can be associated with positive psychological outcomes, reigning or passive acceptance is associated with negative psychological outcomes. Behavioural disengagement refers to a reduction in one's efforts to engage with the stressor or even give up trying to deal with it (Korosec-Serfaty et al., 2022). Another closely related concept is that of attentional disengagement- efforts to redirect one's attention away from the stressor (Korosec-Serfaty et al., 2022). 12 out of 100 participants in Generation Z scored 6-8 (high-very high) in behavioural disengagement. On the other hand, 5 participants from Generation X have scored in the same range. Behavioural disengagement falls under dysfunctional coping style according to Carver (1997). As observed from the results, participants from Generation Z were more likely to resort to behavioural disengagement. Behavioural disengagement has been positively correlated with increased suicidal tendencies and mental health issues (Liang et al., 2020). The third coping mechanism in which there were significant differences in both groups of participants is substance abuse. Substances such as tobacco, alcohol, cocaine and other drugs can be taken to escape reality, reduce anxiety or depression, elevate mood or induce a sense of euphoria, all of which are short-term measures to avoid dealing with stress. Carver (1997) has categorized substance abuse as falling under dysfunctional coping style. 13 participants from Generation Z have scored 6-8 (high-very high) in substance abuse while 6 participants from Generation X have scored in the same range in substance abuse, indicating that substance abuse tendencies in the younger population (18-27 years in this study) are higher compared to their Generation X counterparts. With regard to the perception of stress, there was no significant difference between the two age groups as seen from Table 4. A constant topic of discussion when it comes to stress and its evolution over the years is the difference in generations in terms of tolerance towards stress. The present study showed that there are no significant differences in how the participants from

Generation X and Generation Z perceived stressful situations in their lives. Yet, data from articles such as the India Wellness Index by ICICI Lombard General Insurance and the GOQii India Fit Report's (2022-2023) Stress and Mental Health Study, show that younger generations are indeed more stressed out than their older counterparts. This could be explained by the fact that while younger and older generation could be experiencing a similar amount of stress, younger individuals are more likely to express the fact that they feel stressed out and are more likely to resort to various strategies to cope with it, unlike in older generations who are more likely to deal with stressful situations without overtly expressing being stressed out.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study aimed to compare coping styles and perceptions of stress between individuals of Generation Z and Generation X. While no significant difference was found in the perception of stress between the two age groups, notable distinctions emerged in coping mechanisms. Compared to Generation Z, members in Generation X were more likely to be accepting. On the other hand, individuals from Generation Z had a greater propensity for behavioural disengagement, which is defined as a decrease in efforts to deal with stressors. Furthermore, there was a notable increase in the prevalence of substance misuse among Generation Z members, suggesting a worrying pattern of using unhealthy coping mechanisms among this generation. Reports indicate that younger generations suffer higher levels of stress despite having identical perceptions of stress, perhaps because they are more likely to acknowledge and actively seek out coping techniques. In order to lessen the possible negative consequences of stress on mental health and well-being, this dichotomy emphasizes the significance of addressing generational variations in stress management and encouraging adaptive coping techniques, especially among younger persons. In essence, while the perception of stress may not differ significantly between generations, understanding and addressing variances in coping styles are crucial for fostering resilience and promoting mental wellness across age groups.

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